

Frequency of Operative Deliveries in Primi Obese Patients

Author's Details:

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Abstract:

Objective:-

The objective was to determine the frequency of operative delivery among primigravida with obesity presenting to the tertiary care hospital.

Study Design:-

A cross-sectional study

Setting:-

Gynaecology Unit -I Jinnah Hospital Lahore

Method and Patient:-

For a period of six months from 1st January 2016 to 30th June 2016. 140 primigravidas with obesity presenting with labor and fulfilling the inclusion criteria were enrolled in the study. BMI was calculated on the basis of weight measured in 8 to 12 weeks of gestation and these women were followed comparing their modes of delivery.

Results:

Operative delivery was done in 53(37.86%) women while 87(62.14%) women had normal vaginal delivery. There were 7(13.21%) who had forceps delivery 13(24.53%) vacuum assisted delivery and 33(62.26%) women had lower segment caesarean sections.

Conclusion: -

In this study it was concluded that a high frequency of operative deliveries are observed in obese women i.e. 36%. C-section was the leading operative delivery followed by vacuum assisted delivery in obese women.

Key words:-*Operative delivery, Primigravida, Obesity, Tertiary care hospital.*

INTRODUCTION:-

World Health Organization has declared obesity as a major killer disease of the millennium owing to its dramatic increase in prevalence worldwide.¹ Although there is a higher rate of men in the overweight category, globally more women are in the obese category.²

Worldwide, the obesity, exists at a prevalence of 15-20% and accounts for 2-7% of total healthcare costs.³ Prevalence of obesity in Pakistani women is more than twice as high as in men (20% vs. 7%).⁴

The increasing rate of maternal obesity provides a major challenge to obstetric practice. Maternal obesity increases the risk of a number of pregnancy complications and requires adjustment to routine prenatal care.¹ pre-eclampsia, gestational hypertension, gestational diabetes, thrombo-embolic disease and shoulder dystocia many more established complications due to maternal obesity.⁵

Emergency operative deliveries are added as another component in the spectrum of complications caused by maternal obesity. However, literature regarding this aspect is quite inconsistent. Stephan et al found a frequency of operative deliveries among obese patients as 25.1% with a linear relationship between increase in weight and frequency operative deliveries.⁶

Liaqat et al. showed even a higher frequency of operative deliveries i.e. 30.6% among obese patients.⁷ both these studies concluded that obese women are at much higher risk of operative deliveries. However Vahratian et al reported that the risk of operative deliveries is not as large as previously reported and there is only moderate increase in the risk of operative deliveries among obese.⁸

Similarly, Kaplan-Sturk et al found that obese women (BMI \geq 30), who are otherwise healthy and with normal pregnancies, more commonly deliver vaginally than women with a more normal body weight.⁹

The rationale of this study is to determine the frequency of operative deliveries among primigravida females with obesity presenting to the tertiary care hospital. Obesity has been associated with many adverse fetomaternal outcomes however literature regarding relationship of obesity with operative deliveries had shown considerable variation with few studies showing a positive relationship^{6,7} while another set of studies showing a moderate or no relationship.^{8,9}

Moreover, all these studies have been conducted on both multigravida and primigravida thus giving a limited information regarding the relationship with primigravida exclusively as an operative delivery in primigravida increases the chance of further operative deliveries in subsequent pregnancies. Therefore this study will bridge this gap and will provide information regarding frequency of operative deliveries among primigravida obese patients.

This information will help the obstetricians in decision making regarding the obese patients and considering them as “High Risk” when counselling and risk assessment is done in antenatal clinic and appropriate primary and secondary prophylaxis to achieve better fetomaternal outcome.

A woman who is pregnant for the first time is labelled as primigravida. Females having BMI greater than 30 kg/m² measured at 8 to 12 weeks of gestation by the following formula: BMI= weight/(height in m)². Delivery by any one of the following techniques like LSCS(Lower segment cesarean section) , forceps assisted delivery and vacuum delivery is labelled as Operative delivery.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:-

A cross-sectional study was conducted at Gynaecology Unit -I Jinnah Hospital Lahore for a period of six months from 1st January 2016 to 30th June 2016. 140 primigravidas with obesity presenting with labor and fulfilling the inclusion criteria were enrolled in the study. Non probability consecutive sampling technique was used. BMI was calculated on the basis of weight measured in 8 to 12 weeks of gestation and these women were followed comparing their modes of delivery.

Inclusion Criteria

- Age 18 to 30 years
- Primigravidas with obesity (as per operational definition) presenting to tertiary care hospital Lahore.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients not having their antenatal record.
- Patients with breech presentation determined on abdominal examination and ultrasonography.
- Patients with more than one fetus determined on abdominal examination and ultrasonography.
- Patients who were either known diabetics (diagnosed cases of diabetes before 20 weeks of gestation with fasting blood sugar \geq 126 mg/dl determined from past medical record) or had gestational diabetes (diabetes after 20 weeks of gestation with fasting blood sugar \geq 126 mg/dl)

- Patients with hypertension (Blood pressure (BP) $\geq 140/90$ mmHg before conception and before 20 weeks gestation) or gestational hypertension (BP $\geq 140/90$ mmHg after 20 weeks with previously normal BP)
- Patients with cardiovascular diseases (determined on history, medical record and echocardiography).
- Patients with absolute indications for cesarean section like contracted pelvis and major type placenta previa determined on history, examination and ultrasonography.

Data Collection Procedure

About 140 primigravidas with obesity presenting with labor to the Gynecology unit I Jinnah hospital Lahore and fulfilling the inclusion criteria were approached and an informed consent was taken from them before enrolling in the study. Information regarding their demographic data was obtained by the researcher and was noted in the proforma. Record of antenatal visit was checked and their BMI was calculated on the basis of weight measured in 8 to 12 weeks of gestation. Researcher remained with the patient till the delivery and mode of delivery was also noted in the proforma. Confidentiality of the data was ensured.

RESULTS:-

Mean age of women was 24.30 ± 3.53 years. Minimum and maximum age of women was 18 and 30 years. Mean weight and height of women was 76.95 ± 6.11 kg and 1.53 ± 0.05 meter. Minimum and maximum weight was 67 and 87 kg while minimum and maximum height was 1.47 and 1.69 meter respectively. (**Table-1**) Mean body mass index was 32.77 ± 1.86 . Minimum and maximum BMI of women was 30.18 and 37.78. (**Table-2**) Operative delivery was seen in 110(36.67%) women. While 190(63.33%) women had normal vaginal delivery. (**Figure-1**) Data was stratified for age and in age < 25 years, operative delivery conducted in 63 (38.7%) patients while among females with age ≥ 25 years, operative delivery conducted in 47 (34.3%) patients. The difference was insignificant ($p > 0.05$). (**Table-3**) Data was stratified for BMI of females and in BMI $< 34 \text{ kg/m}^2$, operative delivery conducted in 60 (26.7%) patients while among females with BMI $\geq 34 \text{ kg/m}^2$, operative delivery conducted in 50 (66.7%) patients. The difference was significant ($p < 0.05$). (**Table-4**)

Table - 1

Descriptive statistics for Height, Weight of women

	Weight (Kg)	Height (Meter)
<i>n</i>	140	140
<i>Mean</i>	76.95	1.53
<i>SD</i>	6.11	0.05
<i>Min</i>	67	1.47
<i>Max</i>	87	1.69

Table-2

Descriptive statistics for Body Mass Index of women

	BMI (Kg/m ²)
<i>N</i>	300
<i>Mean</i>	32.77
<i>SD</i>	1.86
<i>Min</i>	30.18
<i>Max</i>	37.78

Table-3

Outcome of delivery stratified for age

		Age group		Total
		<25years	≥25years	
Outcome	Operative delivery	63 (38.7%)	47 (34.3%)	110 (36.7%)
	Normal vaginal delivery	100 (61.3%)	90 (65.7%)	190 (63.3%)
Total		163 (100%)	137 (100%)	300 (100%)

Chi-square = 0.605

p-value = 0.437 (Insignificant)

Figure-1**Outcome of delivery****Table-4****Outcome of delivery stratified for BMI**

		BMI groups		Total
		<34kg/m ²	≥34kg/m ²	
Outcome	Operative delivery	60 (26.7%)	50 (66.7%)	110 (36.7%)
	Normal vaginal delivery	165 (73.3%)	25 (33.3%)	190 (63.3%)
Total		225 (100%)	75 (100%)	300 (100%)

Chi-square = 38.756

p-value = 0.000 (Significant)

DISCUSSION:-

There has been a dramatic rise in worldwide prevalence of obesity, leading to world health organization declaration that obesity is a major killer disease of the millennium. Although there is a higher rate of men in the overweight category, globally more women are in the obese category.²

The increasing rate of maternal obesity provides a major challenge to obstetric practice. Maternal obesity can result in negative outcomes for both women and fetuses. Economic, technologic and life style changes have created an abundance of cheap, high caloric food coupled with reduction in the required physical activity. We are eating more and moving less. Obesity is a significant public health concern and is likely to remain so for the foreseeable future.¹⁰

Worldwide, the obesity, exists at a prevalence of 15-20% and accounts for 2-7% of total healthcare costs.³ Prevalence of obesity in Pakistani women is more than twice as high as in men (20% vs. 7%).⁴

Obesity is associated with increased rates of cesarean section (CS). Several recent reports document rates of CS 32% in USA, 19.1% in Saudi Arabia, 9.29% in Jordan and 20.1% in Iraq. Interestingly also the rates of CS in Baghdad city were 17.9, 19 and 28.7% in 2007, 2009 and 2011; respectively.¹¹⁻¹⁴

Dietz et al. showed that the rate of cesarean section was 14.3% in lean gravid women and 42.6% in obese women.¹⁵ A linear relationship between BMI and cesarean delivery has been reported.¹⁶ Obese women were 6 times more likely to have cesarean section due to cephalo-pelvic disproportion or failure to progress than non-obese women.¹⁷

In this study operative delivery was done in 110(36.67%) women while 190(63.33%) women had normal vaginal delivery. As per findings of a local study from Peshawar showed that among 98 women who were obese among them 30(30.60%) had C-section while 15 had instrumental deliveries in which 11 (11.22%) patients had vacuum delivery and 4 (4.08%) patients had forceps delivery.⁷ Frequency of operative study in this study among obese women was slightly higher than the frequency reported in the local study from Peshawar. However c-section rate in this study is also much more higher than that reported in the local study from Peshawar.

Another study reported that among 17 obese women C-section was done in 10(58.8%)women.¹⁸ In this study c-section rate was higher as that of reported in the mentioned studies before.

Another local study from Karachi reported that among obese women rate of emergency LSCS was significantly higher as that of non-obese women. Among 36 women emergency LSCS was done, 3 women had forceps VO and 10 women had ventose VO.¹⁹

Habiba Sharaf Ali in his study reported the c-section among 48% women who were obese.²⁰ In this study rate of c-section was higher as that of reported by Habiba Sharaf Ali. i.e. 48% vs. 62.26%.

CONCLUSION:-

In this study a high frequency of operative deliveries was observed in obese women i.e. 37.86%. C-section was the leading operative delivery followed by vacuum assisted delivery in obese women. Such patients should be advised for postpartum nutritional counseling, Preconception counseling, careful prenatal management, tight monitoring of weight gain, and long-term follow-up to minimize the social and economic consequences.

Recommendation:-

Such patients should be advised for postpartum nutritional counselling, preconception counselling, careful prenatal management, tight monitoring of weight gain, and long-term follow-up to minimize the social and economic consequences.

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